

UNVEILING ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AT UNIVERSITY OF KHARTOUM: A QUALITATIVE STUDY*

Saifaldin ONIA¹

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18023813

Abstract

Organizational commitment (OC) at universities has recently started to attract growing attention. Therefore, this study sought to explore organizational commitment at University of Khartoum. To meet this purpose, the researcher followed a qualitative research design. To collect data a semi-structured interview was applied with 11 leaders in the University of Khartoum. A thematic analysis method was used to analyze data of the study. The study found that staff members were organizationally committed to the University of Khartoum in general. The implication of this result can help leaders, college officials, and administrators on how they could benefit from the different types of organizational commitment in designing effective human resource policies at the University of Khartoum. The study recommends to enhance staff' organizational commitment, university leaders and officials should design effective human resource policies in the university that can lead to increase the loyalty and obligation to the work and the university.

Key words: *Management, Organizational commitment, Qualitative research, Thematic analysis, University of Khartoum.*

1. Introduction

Organizational commitment (OC) at universities has recently started to attract growing attention (Tekin, Kayacan, and Bektas, 2014). Because the level of staff commitment in higher education is crucial for any change to succeed (Ashkenas, Siegal, and Spiegel, 2013). Due to a staff with a low commitment level often put his interest first instead of his duties and responsibilities (Ganesan *et al.*, 2009), and because committed staff could demonstrate positive work behaviors (Selamat and Nordin, 2012). According to Allen and Mayer (2000), organizational commitment is a psychological state that encourages an employee's engagement with his organization and reduces the likelihood that he will leave. This organizational commitment also identified the degree of loyalty, strength of identity, and obligation towards a common goal and the level of engagement and willingness to make efforts

*This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. Authors retain the copyright of this article.

¹Assistant Professor of Educational Administration, PhD, Faculty of Education University of Khartoum, Sudan, e-mail address: saifonia89@gmail.com, ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7451-7761>

to accomplish that goal (Mowday, Steers, and Porter, 1979; Camp, 1994; Hulpia, Devos, and Rosseel, 2009).

In this respect, some scholars have looked at the staff's OC. Yalcin, Akan, and Yildirim (2021) aimed to investigate the OC of academicians at the Erzincan Binali Yildirim University. According to the results reached in the study, the OC levels of the academicians were at a moderate level. Academicians' emotional commitment is strong, normative, and their attendance commitment was moderate when measured in terms of the sub-dimensions of OC. Bashir and Gani (2020) examine the state of organizational commitment among university teachers in India. This study shows that the majority of teachers have a continuance commitment to their jobs, as they consider the costs and risks of leaving the university, and they will go if given better options.

A study conducted by Lorch (2019) attempted to establish predictors of organizational participation in community college faculty, using Meyer and Allen's three components of this commitment. Overall, however, the data showed high rates of OC from those studied. Kassaw and Golga (2019) assessed the academic staff's level of organizational commitment. The study revealed a moderate level of OC among academic staff at the university.

In addition, Koc (2018) aimed to demonstrate the correlations between academicians' OC and their intention to resign from their job. The study found that academics' intention to leave their job was low. Still, their level of OC was high and they had the most emotional commitment, followed by normative commitment and continuing commitment. Moreover, Koul (2016) examines the teachers' organizational commitment levels in select Government Colleges of Chandigarh. This study aimed at investigating the degree of OC among male and female teachers in government colleges. Commitment ratings for substantive participation were the highest.

Therefore, staff members with high affective commitment are less likely to leave their organizations (Nehmeh, 2009; Vandenberghe & Tremblay, 2008) and value organizational goals and vision (Enriquez, Mc Bride, and Paxton 2001). Also, a high degree of continuance commitment leads staff members to be aware of the costs of discontinuing membership (Reza *et al.*, 2010). Koul (2016) claimed that workers with a robust normative commitment continue to work at the organization as proper behavior and obligation. That is, a lack of OC can reduce organizational effectiveness (Banjarnahor *et al.*, 2018). Hence, leaders often depend on the commitment of their staff (Bennet and Durkin, 2000).

This study uses as its theoretical framework the Meyer and Allen's Model (1990) of organizational commitment. This commitment, according to Meyer and Allen's Model (1990) of organizational commitment (OC) encompassing: affective, normative, and continuance commitment. The affective commitment represents commitment focused on the employee's emotional ties to the organization. The normative commitment represents loyalty to the organization. Continuance commitment reflects commitment based on the perceived costs of leaving the organization (Jaros, 2010). Researchers have used this commitment model to predict significant employee outcomes. Herrbach (2006) stated that Meyer and Allen's Model had been the most widely accepted conceptualization of OC. Cohen and

Lilach (2011) mentioned this model had been the leading approach in studying OC for more than 20 years.

Based on Meyer and Allen's Model of organizational commitment, this study sought to explore the three components of organizational commitment at University of Khartoum. With this purpose, the following basic question was developed to guide the study; how do we determine the organizational commitment at the University of Khartoum?

2. Literature Review

Meyer and Allen's three-component model has been the leading approach in studying organizational commitment (OC) for more than 20 years (Cohen, 2003). It has recently become the most commonly recognized definition of OC (Herrbach, 2006). OC is reflected in at least three general topics, according to Meyer and Allen (1991): active association with the organization, the predictable costs of leaving the organization, and the obligation to stay in the organization. All three methods are referred to as being affective, continuance, and normative commitment.

2.1. Affective Commitment

Affective commitment (AC) refers to an employee's emotional attachment, involvement, and interest in their business (Bryant *et al.*, 2007). AC is also characterized as the employees' willingness to continue to work on an effective and voluntary basis at that organization. Workers who are so committed to their organizations continue to work there because they "want to," not because they "have to" (Nasiri, 2015).

Affective commitment develops when an individual becomes involved in recognizing the value-relevance of or derives their identity from the organization (Alrowwad *et al.*, 2020). For example, employees are considered affectively committed if they feel that the organization treats them fairly, respectfully, and supporting manner (Rego *et al.*, 2004; Esfahani *et al.*, 2014). Affective loyalty is influenced by several factors, according to research. These factors range from organizational characteristics and personal characteristics to work experiences (Alrowwad *et al.*, 2020).

According to Liou (2008), the affective component of organizational commitment described a worker's desire to be with the organization because the worker liked the organization and wanted to work in the organization. The operationally AC may have three causes: individual and organizational interest congruence characterizes as an employee's confidence in and recognition of organizational goals and values; an obsession with helping organizations achieve their goals; and an apparent desire to keep organizational participation out of choice (Ahmad and Rainayee, 2013).

Meyer & Allen (1991) have used affective, continuance, and normative commitment to capturing the multidimensional nature of organizational commitment, AC is considered a more effective measurement of OC. A study conducted by Nazneen and Bhalla (2013) states that affective commitment is considered a more effective measure of OC since it indirectly influences the other two dimensions of OC. According to the findings, faculty members have a moderate degree of affective and continuance engagement and a high level of normative commitment.

2.2. Continuance Commitment

Regarding continuance commitment (CC), the commitment applies to the expected termination costs of an employee (Bryant *et al.*, 2007). Becker (1960) suggests that employees in their organizations invest time, energy, safety, cash, etc. Such investments have a substantial impact on their decisions and plans to leave or stay in their organizations. Accordingly, Sharma and Sinha (2015) argue that an increase in the age and tenure of employees within organizations increases the perceived cost of leaving them when considering the decision to leave their jobs. Employees can also find their insurance, education, job security, and unused holidays. In addition, CC is an attachment to an organization based on an employee's awareness of the costs of discontinuing membership (Reza *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, it is an employee's reluctance to maintain or towards membership in the company. This inertia primarily has two antecedents: commitment (perceived sacrifice) and lack of alternatives (Ahmad and Rainayee, 2013).

In continuance commitment, when an employee realizes that their investment in the company is at risk or that there are no other options available, they develop a determination to stay with the company (Rego *et al.*, 2004). Salary and benefits, retirement programs, skills, social relationships, and missed opportunities are examples of physical, cognitive, and emotional assets (Lambert *et al.*, 2015). Some of the factors that may lead to the development of CC include age, tenure, career satisfaction, and intent (Kont and Jantson, 2014).

Moreover, in continuance commitment, the gains (wage, status, retirement rights, etc.) of the employees in the long term in return for what they give to the organization are essential, together with the fact that the gain of the employees in the long time prevents them from turnover intentions, the economic status, organizational rules (obligatory service, contract, etc.) and culture-based social pressure (inconstancy, incompatibility, etc.) that can lead to long-term commitment (Kiral and Kacar, 2016). According to Gundlach, Achrol, and Mentzer (1995), in CC, employees' confidence that they can receive more benefits from the company as a result of their activities. Furthermore, as CC includes instrumental situations, it can be defined as commitment based on self-seeking. This loyalty is also referred to as a moral obligation, which means remaining part of that organization as it would cost a lot to leave (Balay, 2000).

2.3. Normative Commitment

Normative commitment (NC) reflects the obligation of an employee to remain in his organization (Bryant *et al.*, 2007). Likewise, organizational culture, rewards, punishments, and autonomy of employees play a vital role in determining the level of NC (Meyer and Allen, 1997; Chang, 2002; Harr and Spell, 2004; Sharma and Sinha, 2015). Buchko *et al.* (1998) characterized normative loyalty in this context as an obligation to stay with an organization. Therefore, it may be the consequence of an internalized norm developed by the person before joining the organization through the values inherent or other socialization processes. One should be loyal to one's organization (Ahmad and Rainayee, 2013).

Individuals establish normative commitment when they socialize the organization's norms, obtain rewards that make them feel compelled to reciprocate

or accept the terms of a psychological contract. This can result from the process of internalization individuals undergo before or after joining the organization (Rego *et al.*, 2004). Some of the most critical factors that influence the way NC is experienced are leadership and culture. Leadership plays a significant role in inducing NC by demonstrating high moral standards, honesty, and integrity. With regards to culture, different cultural factors influence the interpretation and implications of NC in different ways. For example, the findings proposed by Fischer and Mansell (2009) indicate that NC is expected to be greater and related more strongly to behaviors in collectivist cultures as opposed to individualistic cultures.

A study conducted by Koul (2016) claimed that workers with a solid normative commitment found it their responsibility to work at the organization and continue working at the organization as proper behavior and obligation because of their values and ideologies. NC has its antecedents in an employee's values as determined by their cultural, social, and familial background and prior experiences. In more precise terms, NC could be focused on organizational commitment in an employee who then feels a moral obligation to stay with the organization based on social or cultural expectations of the employee and assumes one should be loyal to the organization (Mosadeghrad, Ferlie, and Rosenberg, 2008).

3. Methodology

This study followed a qualitative research which is the collection, analysis, and interpretation of comprehensive narrative and visual (i.e., nonnumerical) data to gain insights into a particular phenomenon of interest (Gay, 2012). It provides an opportunity for the researcher to involve the respondents in projective techniques. Therefore, this method was used in this study through interviews with the high administration at the University of Khartoum to gather descriptive information about their attitudes, opinions, and ideas concerning the variable under study.

The participants for in-depth interviews were selected purposely in a qualitative method that helped a researcher pick units from a population they are interested in studying, based on the researcher's subjective judgment. The purposive sampling was used with the 11 participants, including college deans, deputy deans, department heads in the University of Khartoum. The participants were anonymized by using codes instead of their real names.

Consequently, to ask additional probe questions to analyze the issue in-depth and understand the reasons behind participants' answers, a semi-structured interview is used in this study. The semi-structured interview allowed the researcher to analyze the data thematically.

To analyze the answers of the semi-structured interview, the researcher used the thematic analysis method. The reason for using thematic analysis it led a researcher to define, organizing, and providing insight into patterns of meaning (themes) across a data set; therefore, classify those critical for the answer to a specific research question. The six steps that researcher followed in thematic analysis method were: first, the researcher familiarized himself with the data that collected from participants; to understand the participants' real social experience involves qualitative data analytical approaches that decide upon the themes, under which the data will be labelled, sorted, compared, and

synthesized (Ritchie *et al.*, 2013). Second, initial codes were generated from data; each participant's answers were separated into meaningful categories, named, and coded as P1, P2, P3, to P11 where "P" refers to the participant. Third, the researcher searched for themes. Fourth, the potential themes were reviewed. Fifth, themes were defined and named; without thematic categories, the researcher has nothing to describe, nothing to compare, and nothing to explain (Ryan and Bernard, 2003). Sixth, producing the report (the findings); when introducing results, the researcher used different ways to keep participants' anonymity and privacy, using general terms like one dean, deputy dean, one department head, one professor, etc.

4. Results

A qualitative data collected through the interview from the leaders were analyzed under the three dimensions (affective, continuance, and normative) presented below. In the overall view, most of the interviewees agreed that the University of Khartoum staff members are committed to the university (P5, P10, P11). Among the interviewees, one professor (P1) stated that:

There are moderate and high levels of organizational engagement at the University of Khartoum, but the moderate is the most popular because the commitment depends on job appreciation.

From the above quote, the staff members who appreciate their jobs are more committed than others who do not. One interviewee stated that the low salaries are the leading cause for those who do not understand their position, reflecting in their less commitment. In this regard, one dean (P3) mentioned that:

There are disparities in staff organizational commitment at the University of Khartoum. I mean there is reasonable and low commitment. He further elaborated exemplary commitment comes from an appreciation of the university and feeling comfortable with the work. Low commitment backs to the frustration that staff members think from low income they receive.

Moreover, one professor (P2) defended the University of Khartoum staff members and said that staff are committed to all three dimensions of organizational commitment. He further detailed that:

The University of Khartoum's staff is highly dedicated to the organization. He explained that there is a commitment to the goals, systems, and laws (normative commitment), commitment to the work (continuance commitment), and a desire to remain at the University (affective commitment). As a result, I can say there is a high level of organizational commitment among the staff at the University of Khartoum.

As put in the professor reflection above, the University of Khartoum staff members are committed to the university. The three dimensions of staff commitment: affective, continuance, and normative commitment were reflected. These dimensions are presented in detail below.

4.1. Affective commitment

Affective commitment is the first dimension of organizational commitment. According to interview answers, most of the interviewees stated that recognition of the

university's vision and goals is most determined by staff affective commitment. They also, mentioned that staff awareness which represents knowing policies, situations, documents, or any other important information of the university is an essential factor of staff commitment. One department head (P6) said: *"It can be described as good because most staff members have a high level of awareness and commitment to serving the university. They value the vision and goals of the university"*.

Similar to what was mentioned above, one department head (P8) that *"there is a high responsibility from staff members towards their works"*. This work responsibility leads to produce a high performance which results in more affective commitment. Affective engagement has been shown to have the most vital positive relationship with positive job habits. It remains an essential factor in crucial outcomes such as work success and productivity.

Moreover, one interviewee (P7) reflected own its opinion as *"To some extent, there is an organizational commitment among staff members of the University of Khartoum. He explained that some of them have passion and belonging to the university (affective commitment)"*.

Furthermore, some interviewees mentioned that the staffs of the University of Khartoum have a desire to work, so they expected to have a level of productivity and commitment. Because they feel that the university treats them in a fair, respectful, and supportive manner. One professor (P2) stated that *"Based on my extensive experience working at this university, I touched that staff members have strong desire to remain at the university (affective commitment)"*.

In line with what the professor mentioned above, one department head (P9) said: *"Yes, the faculty members at the University of Khartoum have a strong commitment. There is affective commitment, where most of the staff members don't have a desire to transform to another University"*.

Based on the above participants' perspectives, when the staff members have a desire to work, *passion, and belonging, it means that they have a level of affective commitment to the university.*

4.2. Continuance commitment

According to the interview result, staffs continuance commitment depends on the job income on the one hand, and the absence of alternatives exists other than remaining in the university on the other hand as one deputy-dean (P4) detailed that:

Staff members at the University of Khartoum are moderately committed to the organization. I mean, staff members have a continuance commitment at the University of Khartoum partially. They are remaining in the university because they recognize the cost of leaving and finding another job with satisfied payment.

Consistent with what was mentioned above, one department head (P7) said:

In my opinion, several faculty members have purely materialistic views of the university (continuance commitment). They continue to their work because they do not have other options; I believe when finding other choices, they will leave. Especially if they get a chance to migrate to one of the Gulf countries, they immediately will leave without any hesitation.

So, it is evident that the continuance commitment among staff members of the University of Khartoum seemed to be low since it depends on the job income, and when given better alternatives, they may leave their university.

4.3. Normative commitment

Most of the interviewees agreed that staff in the University of Khartoum have an exemplary normative commitment since they feel a moral obligation to stay with the university based on their values, ideologies and social or cultural expectations of the university as the department head (P8) stated that:

I feel like this university is my home. He added I love everything in this university, so, I will do my best to achieve its objectives. I noted most staff members have great sense towards the goals and objectives of the University of Khartoum (normative commitment).

Similar to the above quote, another department head (P9) reflected that:

Yes, there is an outstanding commitment towards the faculty and University of Khartoum, where staff members respect the organizational culture, traditions of the university, norms, and goals of the University. So, I believe there is a reasonable normative commitment among the staff members.

Therefore, having all characteristics mentioned in the above reflections that the staff members at the University of Khartoum have good normative commitments which implies they value the norms and culture of the University of Khartoum.

Generally, from all quotes of the results of the interviews mentioned above, it can be concluded that there are disparities in staffs' organizational commitment at the University of Khartoum between low and high. The low commitment backs to the frustration that staff members feel from the low income they receive. But there is a great extent of organizational commitment among staff members of the University of Khartoum. So, it can be described as good from the reality that most of the staff members have a high degree of awareness and commitment that serve the university.

5. Discussion

Describing the organizational commitment at the University of Khartoum was the fundamental research question expected to be dealt with. To illustrate the level of staff organizational commitment, the study adopted Meyer and Allen's Model (1990) of organizational commitment. This model suggests that the worker encounters organizational commitment as three overlapping mindsets encompassing: affective, normative, and continuance organizational commitment. The affective commitment represents engagement focused on the employee's emotional ties to the organization. Normative commitment means loyalty to the organization. Continuance commitment reflects commitment based on the perceived costs of leaving the organization (Jaros, 2010).

According to the analysis of qualitative data collected through interviews indicated that the staff members are committed to the University of Khartoum. One interviewee stated that there is an organizational commitment among staff members of the University of Khartoum to the great extent. He explained that there is a

commitment to the objectives, systems, and laws (normative commitment), there is a commitment to the work (continuance commitment). Also, there is a desire to stay in the University (affective commitment). So, there is a high degree of staff organizational commitment at the University of Khartoum. Therefore, the staff members of the University of Khartoum are committed to the university.

Supporting the result of current study, Lorch (2019) attempted to establish predictors of organizational participation in community college faculty, using Meyer and Allen's three components of this commitment. Overall, however, the data showed high rates of organizational commitment from those studied. Bano, Ishrat, and Mishra (2019) found a high level of organizational commitment leads to improvement in an employee's performance and efficiency in accomplishing the organization's tasks and goals. Another study by Bin Jomah (2017) was carried out to establish the validity of psychological empowerment in improving the commitment levels among institutions. The study results indicated that organizational commitment relied heavily on the level of autonomy given to the employee in decision-making at the workplace.

Furthermore, Yahaya, Chek, Samsudin, and Jizat (2014) also designed a study to investigate the level of organizational commitment in Malaysian public higher education. Overall, the result revealed that the commitment level of faculty members was high. Nazneen and Bhalla (2013) discovered that public university faculty members have a high organizational commitment and dominant organizational commitments are normative and affective commitments. Malik, Waheed, and Malik (2010) explored a high degree of organizational engagement among Pakistani university faculty members.

Contrary to the result of the current study, Alrowwad *et al.* (2020) demonstrated a low level of attitude regarding the academic staff committed to their university at Zarqa University in Jordan. Fika, Ibi, and Abdulrahman (2016) carried out a study to determine the relationship between staff utilization and staff commitment in Borno State Colleges of Education, Nigeria, and assess staff commitment in Borno State Colleges of Education. The result of the study revealed that the level of staff commitment in Borno State Colleges of Education was low. Another study was conducted by Kassaw and Golga (2019) to assess the academic staff's level of organizational commitment. The study revealed a moderate level of organizational commitment among academic staff at the university.

Hereunder, the results of components of organizational commitment, which include affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment are discussed in detail.

Regarding to affective commitment, the analysis of qualitative data generated from interviewees indicated that some of the participants mentioned that the staff members of the University of Khartoum have a desire to work, so they expected to have a level of productivity and commitment. One participant said: based on my long experience working at this university, I've noticed that employees have a strong desire to stay here. Nasiri (2015) stated that workers who are so committed to their organizations continue to work there because they "want to," not because they "have to". Also, another interviewee reflected that the affective commitment can be described as good because most of the staff members have a high degree of awareness and commitment that serve the university. They have appraisal the

university's vision and goals. Enriquez, Mc Bride, and Paxton (2001) explain that employees' value organizational goals, vision, and sense of independence are three determinants of the level of effective commitment of the employees.

Similarly, the qualitative results confirmed that staffs continuance commitment depends on the job income on the one hand and the absence of alternatives on the other hands. Ahmad and Rainayee (2013) stated employee's reluctant to maintain or towards membership in the company and this inertia primarily has two antecedents: commitment (perceived sacrifice) and lack of alternatives. Bashir and Gani (2020) highlighted that teachers had high continuance commitment, as the teachers were not willing to leave the university and were fully aware of the costs and benefits of parting from the university. Yalcin, Akan, and Yildirim (2021) found that the continuance commitment of the academicians was at a moderate level. Also, Turkkan and Yalcintas (2017) found that continuance commitment was found to be at a medium level.

Concerning with normative commitment, the qualitative analysis uncovered that most of the interviewees agreed that staff in the University of Khartoum have an exemplary normative commitment as one participant stated that: I feel like this university is my home. He added I love everything in this university, so, I will do my best to achieve its objectives. Another interviewee reflected an outstanding commitment towards the faculty and University of Khartoum, where staff members respect the organizational culture, tradition of the university, norms, and goals of the University. So, there is a reasonable normative commitment among the staff members. Contrary to this result, Bashir and Gani (2020) revealed that teachers felt less obliged to stay in the institution and were having less normative commitment. Yalcin, Akan, and Yildirim (2021) aimed to investigate the organizational commitment of academicians at the Erzincan Binali Yildirim University in Turkey. They found that the normative commitment of the academicians was at a moderate level.

6. Conclusion

This study was designed to unveil organizational commitment in the University of Khartoum. According to the study's findings, staff members were organizationally committed to the University of Khartoum in general. Therefore, in its sub-dimensions, staff members were affectively and normatively committed to the University of Khartoum. That is meant; the staff members are emotionally attached, engaged, participate in all activities in the university, and recognize goals and values of the university and obligation to remain with an organization. On the other hand, staff members were less continuance committed at the University of Khartoum. This may back to the frustration that staff members feel from the low income and the lack of job alternatives.

The implication of these results can help leaders, college officials, and administrators on how they could benefit from the different types of organizational commitment in designing effective human resource policies at the University of Khartoum. Besides, the results of this study may have its practical implication for leaders and officials in the University of Khartoum in drafting of laws on the work-life of staff members at the university setting.

Based on the study's findings, the study recommends improving staffs' commitment; because committed staff members can accomplish the goals and vision effectively. So, to enhance staffs' organizational commitment, university leaders and officials should design effective human resource policies in the university that can lead to increase the loyalty and obligation to the work and the university. The University of Khartoum should improve staff continuance commitment through acknowledgment, compensation, and incentive packages. University leaders and officials should work to enhance the materialistic position of staff members at the University of Khartoum to reduce migration. In addition, officials should exert efforts to draft policies and laws that can help to improve the work-life of staff members in the university.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmad, A., & Rainayee, R.A. (2013). Exploring a Common Theme of Organizational Commitment: A Way to Consensuses. *Pacific Business Review International*, 67-68.
2. Allen, N.J. & Meyer, J.P. (1990). The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63(1), 1-18.
3. Allen, N.J., & Meyer, J.P. (2000). Construct validation in organizational behavior research: the case of organizational commitment. In Guftin, R.D and Helmes, E. (Eds.), *Problems and solutions in Human Assessment: Honoring Douglas N.* (pp. 285-314).
4. Alrowwad, A., Almajali, D., Masa'deh, R., Obeidat, B., & Aqqad, N. (2020). The role of organizational commitment in enhancing organizational effectiveness. In *33rd Ibima Conference: Granada, Spain*. Retrieved from https://ibima.org/accepted_paper/the-role-of-organizational-commitment-in-enhancing-organizational-effectiveness.
5. Ashkenas, R., Siegal, W., & Spiegel, N. (2013). Mastering organizational complexity: A core competency for 21st century leaders. *Research in Organizational Change and Development*, 21, 29-58.
6. Balay, R. (2000). *Organizational Commitment of managers and teachers*. Nobel Publications, Ankara.
7. Banjarnahor, H., Hutabarat, W., Sibuea, A.M., & Situmorang, M. (2018). Job Satisfaction as a Mediator between Directive and Participatory Leadership Styles toward Organizational Commitment. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11(4), 869-888.
8. Bano, K., Ishrat, A., & Mishra, K.K. (2019). Factors affect-ing organizational commitment of teachers in gov-ernment and private universities. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 8(11), 138-152.
9. Bashir, B., & Gani, A. (2020). Correlates of Organisational Commitment Among University Teachers in India: An Empirical Investigation. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Management Research and Innovation*, 16(1), 7-20.
10. Becker, H.S. (1960). Notes on the concept of commitment. *American Journal of Sociology*, 66 (1), 32 -40.

11. Bennet, H. & Durkin, M. (2000). The effects of organizational change on employee psychological attachment. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 15(2): 126–147.
12. Bin Jomah, N. (2017). Psychological Empowerment on Organizational Commitment as Perceived by Saudi Academics. *World Journal of Education*, 7(1), 83-92.
13. Bryant, S., Moshavi, D., & Nguyen, T. (2007). Afield study on organizational commitment, professional commitment and peer mentoring. *Database for advances in information systems*, 38(2).
14. Buchko, Aoran, A., Weinzimmer, Laurence G. and Sergejev, Alexander V. (1998).“Effects of cultural context on the antecedents, correlates, and consequences of organizational commitment: A study of Russian workers”, *Journal of Business Research*, 43, 109- 116.
15. Camp, S.D. (1994). Assessing the effects of organizational commitment and job satisfaction on turnover: An event history approach.*The Prison Journal* 74(3).
16. Chang, E. (2002). Distributive Justice and organizational commitment revisited: moderation by layoff in the case of Korean employees. *Human Resources Management*, 41(2).
17. Cohen, A. & Lilach, C. (2011). Individual values, organizational commitment, and participation in change: Israeli teachers’ approach to an optional educational reform. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 26, 385–396.
18. Cohen, A. (2003). *Multiple commitments in the workplace: An integrative approach*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
19. Enriquez, V., Mc Bride, J., & Paxton, L. (2001). Improving knowledge of strategic goals and the impact on organizational commitment. *Health Marketing Quarterly*, 18(3/4).
20. Esfahani, A.N., Ghasemi, R.A., & Tabrizi, A.T. (2014). The Relationship between Management Credibility and Affective Commitment in Consultant Engineering Firms: Evidence from Iranian Organizations. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 143, 947-952.
21. Fika, I.B., Ibi, M.B., & Abdulrahman, A. (2016). Staff Utilization and Commitment in Borno State Colleges of Education, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(20), 68-74.
22. Fischer, R., & Mansell, A. (2009). Commitment across Cultures: A Meta-Analytical Approach. *Journal of International Business Studies*, 40, 1339-1358.
23. Ganesan, S., George, M., Jap, S., Palmatier, R.W., & Weitz, B. (2009). Supply chain management and retailer performance: emerging trends, issues, and implications for research and practice. *Journal of retailing*, 85(1), 84-94.
24. Gay, L.R. (2012). *Educational Research: competencies for analysis and application*. Second Edition, Columbus: Charles E. Merrill publishing Company.
25. Gundlach, G.T., Achrol, R.S., & Mentzer, J.T. (1995). The structure of commitment in exchange. *Journal of Marketing*, 59(1), 78-92.
26. Harr, J., & Spell, C. (2004). Program knowledge and value of work.Family practice and organizational commitment. *The international journal of human resources management*, 15(6).

27. Herrbach, O. (2006). A matter of feeling? The affective tone of organizational commitment and identification. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 27(5), 629–643.
28. Hulpia, H., Devos, G., & Rosseel, Y. (2009). The relationship between the perception of distributed leadership in secondary schools and teachers' and teacher leaders' job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 20(3), 291-317.
29. Jaros, S. (2010). Commitment to organizational change: a critical review. *Journal of Change Management*, 10, 79–108.
30. Kassaw, E.S., & Golga, D.N. (2019). *Academic Staffs' Level of Organizational Commitment in Higher Educational Setting: The Case of Haramaya University*.
31. Kiral, E., & Kacar, O. (2016). The relationship between teachers' school commitment and school culture. *International Education Studies*, 9(12), 90-108.
32. Koc, M. (2018). Research on Correlations between Academicians' Levels of Organizational Commitment and Their Intention to Quit Their Job: A Comparison of State and Foundation Universities. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 7(1), 163-173.
33. Kont, K-R., & Jantson, S. (2014). Organizational Commitment in Estonian University Libraries: A Review and Survey. *New Review of Academic Librarianship*, 20(3), 296-319.
34. Koul, N. (2016). Evaluation of Organization Commitment of Teachers: A Study in Select Government Colleges of Chandigarh. *Journal of Business and Management*, 18(12), 11-15.
35. Lambert, E.G., Hogan, N.L., & Keena, L.D. (2015). The Impact of Job Attitudes on Private Correctional Staff's Continuance and Affective Organizational Commitment. *Journal of Applied Security Research*, 10(1), 1-22.
36. Liou, S. (2008). An analysis of the concept of organizational commitment. *Nursing Forum*, 43(3), 116-125.
37. Lorch, C.A. (2019). *Identifying Predictors of Organizational Commitment Among Community College Faculty Members in Arkansas*. Graduate Theses and Dissertations Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.uark.edu/etd/3156>.
38. Malik, O.F., Waheed, A., & Malik, K.R., (2010), “*The Mediating Effects of Job Satisfaction on Role Stressors and Affective Commitment*”, *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(11). <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v5n11p223>
39. Meyer, J. & Allen, N. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61-89.
40. Meyer, J., & Allen, N. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
41. Mosadeghrad, A. M., Ferlie, E., & Rosenberg, D. (2008). A study of the relationship between job satisfaction, organizational commitment and turnover intention among hospital employees. *Health services management research*, 21(4), 211-227.
42. Mowday, R.T., Steers, R.M., & Porter, L.W. (1979). The measurement of organizational commitment. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 14(2), 224-247.

43. Nasiri, M. (2015). The Survey of Conceptual Modeling of Causal Relationship between Organization Commitment with Organizational Citizenship Behavior in Campus Recreation Administrations. *International Journal of Sport Studies*, 5(6), 653-658.
44. Nazneen, A. & Bhalla, P. (2013). A Comparative Study of ORS and Job satisfaction among male and female employees of Organized Retail Sector. *International Journal Of Business Management and Research*, 3(4), pp 19-28.
45. Nehmeh, R. (2009). *What is organizational commitment, why should managers want it in their workforce and is there any cost effective way to secure it?* Swiss Management University, Swiss Management Center.
46. Rego, A., Leite, R., Carvalho, T., Freire, C., & Vieira, A. (2004). Organizational Commitment: Toward a Different Understanding of the Ways People Feel Attached to their Organizations. *Management Research: Journal of the Iberoamerican Academy of Management*, 2(3), 201-218.
47. Reza, B., Jandaghi, G., Zarei, H., & Dastani, M.N. (2010). An examination of the relationship between empowerment and organizational commitment. *International Journal of Human Science*, 7(2).
48. Ritchie, J., Ormston, R., McNaughton Nicholls, C., & Lewis, J. (2013). *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers*.
49. Ryan, G.W. and Bernard, H.R. (2003). Data management and analysis methods. In Denzin, N. and Lincoln, Y.(eds.), *Handbook of qualitative research*(2nd ed.), Sage Publications, Inc. Thousand Oaks.
50. Selamat, N., & Nordin, N. (2012). *A study on teacher's commitment and emotional intelligence in the district of Klang*.
51. Sharma, P., & Sinha, V. (2015). The influence of occupational rank on organizational commitment of faculty members. *Management*, 20(2).
52. Tekin, M., Kayacan, E., & Bektaş, H. (2014). Organizational commitment: an empirical investigation of scholars in Turkish public universities. *Istanbul University Econometrics and Statistics e-Journal*, 21, 69-80.
53. Turkkan, E. and Yalcintas, M. (2017). Investigation of the relationship between organizational culture and organizational commitment: Istanbul Commerce University. *Research Journal of Business and Management (RJBM)*, 4(2), 194-202.
54. Vandenberghe, C., & Tremblay, M. (2008). The role of pay satisfaction and organizational commitment in turnover intentions: A two-sample study. *Journal of Business Psychology*, 22, 275-286.
55. Yahaya, R., Chek, I.T., Samsudin, N., & Jizat, J.E. M. (2014). Organizational commitment at a higher education institution. *International Journal of education and research*, 2(11), 309-318.
56. Yalcin, S., Akan, D., & Yildirim, I. (2021). Investigation of the organizational commitment and psychological well-being levels of academicians. *International Journal of Research in Education and Science (IJRES)*, 7(2), 525-544. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijres.1346>.